

Working paper: Comparative analysis for masonry interlocking skewed arches

The main objective of this work is to study the structural behaviour of interlocking skewed arch using the static problem based on the lower bound limit analysis; and discrete element analysis.

The main novel contributions of the paper will be:

- studying two helicoidal and logarithmic bond patterns

- Investigating different numbers and orientations for the joints

- Modelling interlocking joints in the local u or v directions of the shell.

